

PSYCHOSOCIAL CORRELATES OF BURNOUT AMONG MIDWIVES IN SELECTED PUBLIC HEALTH FACILITIES IN ABIA STATE.

Enwereji-Emeka, Victoria Uchechi, Prof P. Ukaigwe and Prof Mkpe Abbey

*African Centre of Excellence in Public Health and Toxicological Research University of Port
Harcourt*

Email: patricia.ukaigwe@uniport.edu.ng, mkpeabbey@aol.com.

Phone Number: 08033381042, +2347083362421.

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<p>Keywords: <i>Psychosocial, Burnout, Midwives, Public health facilities.</i></p>	<p>Abstract: Background: <i>Midwives employed in public health facilities especially in developing countries face elevated burnout levels due to issues like inadequate staff, personality and emotional problems. This study investigated the psychosocial correlates of burnout among midwives in selected public health facilities in Abia State.</i></p> <p>Aim: <i>The aim of this study is to investigate psychosocial correlates of burnout among midwives in public health facilities in Abia State.</i></p> <p>Methods: <i>Quantitative data were collected using a structured questionnaire.</i></p> <p>Results: <i>The study revealed that personality traits played a significant role in the development of burnout in midwives. Midwives who had moderate neuroticism ($p=0.002$), extraversion ($p=0.001$), and conscientiousness ($p=0.001$) were more likely to experience burnout, while those who scored high on agreeableness were more likely to experience emotional exhaustion ($p=0.001$) and reduced personal accomplishment ($p=0.005$). Emotional intelligence was significantly associated with burnout among midwives. Midwives who experienced burnout tend to have moderate levels of emotional intelligence, with some scoring high on dimensions such as self-management (55.80%) and self-motivation (51.20%), while others scored lower on dimensions such as self-awareness (8.50%) and relationship management (5.60%). Midwives who scored low on emotional intelligence were more likely to experience emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment.</i></p> <p>Conclusion: <i>The study concluded that personality traits and emotional intelligence played a major role in the development of burnout and recommended that there is need for</i></p>
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healthcare organizations to prioritize the well-being of midwives by implementing interventions that address the psychosocial factors of burnout.

Introduction

The need for skilled midwives at every birth has been identified as the remedy in the reduction of maternal mortality. Although remarkable progress has been made in reducing maternal mortality in developed countries, in the low and middle-income countries, it remained significantly high, which accounts for 94 percent of maternal death (United Nations, 2020). The Federal Republic of Nigeria in 2023 had high maternal mortality rate of 1,047 deaths per 100,000 live births (World Health Organization report, 2023) and a low number of midwives, which undermines the achievement of goal 3 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for 2030, especially the health of the mother and new-born. This high mortality indirectly focuses global attention on skilled workers and much more on nurse-midwives who with professional expertise and improved quality of care can avert maternal and newborn mortality in all health care settings (WHO, 2022). But while striving to achieve a reduction in mortality by utilizing midwives as the key frontline workers, little attention is paid to the stress and burnout experienced by them. Geraghty et al. (2019) opined that in clinical environment, midwives experience burnout and stress which could affect their health emotionally, physically and psychologically as well as impair their practices in the hospital.

Midwives play a vital role in the healthcare delivery system, particularly in the area of

maternal and child health (Fumagalli et al., 2024). They are responsible for providing prenatal, intrapartum, and postpartum care to women, as well as conducting deliveries and providing family planning services. Despite their critical role in the healthcare system, midwives are often exposed to a range of stressful and traumatic events, including high-risk pregnancies, complicated deliveries, and maternal and infant mortality (Hildingsson et al., 2024). These experiences can take a toll on their physical and mental health, leading to burnout.

Research indicates that midwives employed in public health facilities may face elevated burnout levels due to systemic issues such as understaffing, restricted professional autonomy, and inadequate support from healthcare administrators (Hildingsson et al., 2024). It has been argued that midwives continuing exposure to stressors, providing care for serious and terminally ill patients, disruption of sleep, witnessing or hearing about traumatic events during pregnancy, childbirth, and postpartum period, results in a psychophysical condition called burnout (Sidhu et al., 2020). Burnout is a state of emotional, mental, and physical exhaustion caused by prolonged stress, overwork, and lack of balance in life (Edú-Valsania et al., 2022).

According to Edú-Valsania et al. (2022), burnout is comprised of three dimensions; emotional exhaustion, which is characterized by the lack of

enthusiasm, energy and depletion of emotional resources; depersonalization, which can be described as the negative attitudes toward colleagues, patients/clients, and the organization; and also reduced personal accomplishment, which is significantly manifested as a worker's tendency towards negative self-evaluation and also showing dissatisfaction with their performance at the place of work.

The psychosocial factors in an organization that can lead to stress, burnout, or other health problems include the following; excessive demands from work place, poor working conditions, poor working relationships and management, lack of support from colleagues and supervisors, physical or verbal violence and lack of control over the demands of a particular job (Maslach; Schaufeli, & Leiter 2001).

In as much as various studies have shown that the increased burden of work-related burnout is a public health issue, however, little attention is given to the problem. Particularly, in developing nations, healthcare workers don't receive enough psychological and social care from the health management system. Additionally, there is a very limited data indicating the psychosocial correlates of burnout among Nigerian midwives especially how personality traits and emotional intelligence relate to burnout. Generating evidence on this is a vital step in mitigating the problem's far-reaching consequences of burnout, offers insights on focusing midwives' mental health, and improves the quality of maternity care, ultimately helping to achieve the maternal, neonatal, and child health-related sustainable

development goals (SDGs). However, the main aim of this study is to examine the psychosocial correlates of burnout among midwives in selected health care facilities in Abia State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were used to guide this research study;

1. To what extent does personality traits relate to burnout among midwives in public health facilities in Abia State?
2. To what extent does emotional intelligence relate to burnout among midwives in public health facilities in Abia State?.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance were formulated to guide this study;

1. Personality traits do not relate to burnout among midwives in public health facilities in Abia State.
2. Emotional intelligence do not relate to burnout among midwives in public health facilities in Abia State.

Methodology

The design adopted for the study was a correlation research design. The population of study comprised of all the registered licensed midwives working in three selected health facilities in Abia State consisting of Abia State University Teaching Hospital Aba, Abia Specialist and Diagnostic Centre Nigeria Umuahia and Federal Medical Centre probability. The sample size was 435 which was determined using Kothari (2004)'s formular.

The sampling technique adopted was convenient and purposive sampling. The research instruments used for data collection was a structured questionnaire including Emotional intelligence inventory (EI) by Akintoye (2005), Maslach Burnout Scale (MBS) developed by Maslach (1996), Personality Inventory (NEO) developed by Costa and McCrae (1992). The questionnaire was divided into 4 sections A, B, C and D. Section A was used to collect bio-data information from participants. The section B carried the items that measured the personality trait with the Revised Neo-Personality Inventory (Neo-Pi-R) with 30 items. It was used to assess personality traits (Neuroticism, Extraversion and Openness to Experience) of respondents. Section C measured the emotional intelligence of the participants using emotional intelligent scale with 30 items which are self-awareness, self-management, self-motivation, social awareness and relationship management. Section D

measured Burnout using the Maslach burnout scale with 13 items which measured the dimensions of burnout. The instruments were administered on the participants by the researcher, assisted by six research assistants who were briefed on the method and mode of approach to the participants, as well as the importance of confidentiality of their responses. Out 345 that received the questionnaire, 325 returned them giving a 93% retrieval rate. The quantitative research questions were answered with mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested with multiple logistic regression associated with independent sample t-test statistics. Ethical approval to conduct the study was first granted by the University of Port Harcourt ethical committee number UPH/CEREMAD/REC/MM99/019. Ethical permission was also obtained to collect data for this study by the research and ethics committee of the hospitals used for the study.

Results

Table 1: Burnout levels of the midwives

Variable (N = 325)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Emotional exhaustion		
Low	69	21.20
Moderate	177	54.24
High	79	24.56
Depersonalization		
Low	117	35.88
Moderate	191	58.71
High	17	5.41
Reduced personal accomplishment		
Low	217	66.81
Moderate	94	28.95

High

17

4.24

The Table 1 presents the burnout levels of midwives, with three dimensions of burnout being measured: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. The result showed that 54.24% (n=177) of the midwives experienced a moderate level of emotional exhaustion. Furthermore, the Table revealed that 24.56% (n=79) of the midwives had a high level of emotional exhaustion. On the other hand, 21.20% (n=69) of the midwives exhibited a low level of emotional exhaustion. The Table also showed that 58.71% (n=191) of the midwives had a moderate level of depersonalization, 5.41% (n=17) of the midwives

recorded a high level of depersonalization. However, 35.88% (n=117) of the midwives exhibited low level of depersonalization. Table:1 also revealed that 66.81% (n=217) of the midwives recorded a low level in reduced personal accomplishment. Furthermore, 4.24% (n=14) of the midwives had a high level in reduced personal accomplishment, indicating that they experience high levels of reduced personal accomplishment. On the other hand, 28.75% (n=94) of the midwives had a moderate level of reduced personal accomplishment, which suggest that they experience low levels of reduced personal accomplishment.

Table 2: Association between personality trait and burnout

Personality trait	Level of emotional exhaustion (n=325)			COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)	P-value
	Low	Moderate	High			
Neuroticism	1 (0.31%)	20 (6.15%)	5 (1.54%)	2.65 (1.70 – 3.94)	2.02 (1.48 – 2.82)	0.002
Openness to experience	4 (1.23%)	31 (9.54%)	10 (3.08%)	1.42 (1.08 – 2.10)	0.94 (0.15 – 1.31)	0.710
Extraversion	4 (1.23%)	11 (3.38%)	8 (2.46%)	1.18 (0.95 – 1.33)	1.61 (0.82 – 1.48)	0.101
Agreeableness	9 (2.78%)	94 (28.90%)	33 (10.15%)	2.51 (1.77 – 3.85)	2.10 (1.52 – 2.81)	0.003
Conscientiousness	6 (1.85%)	60 (18.46%)	29 (8.94%)	4.58 (2.12 – 7.17)	2.37 (1.02 – 4.81)	0.001
Depersonalization (n=325)						
	Low	Moderate	High			
Neuroticism	2 (0.62%)	18 (5.54%)	16 (4.92%)	2.10 (1.21 – 2.58)	2.01 (1.31 – 2.80)	0.005
Openness to experience	6 (1.85%)	16 (4.92%)	10 (3.08%)	1.32 (1.11 – 2.05)	0.99 (0.81 – 1.85)	0.406

Extraversion	3 (0.92%)	25 (7.69%)	30 (9.23%)	1.05 (0.71 – 1.35)	1.04 (0.72 – 1.50)	0.002
Agreeableness	2 (0.62%)	88 (27.08%)	26 (8.00%)	1.08 (0.83 – 1.88)	0.88 (0.62 – 1.35)	0.210
Conscientiousness	4 (1.23%)	62 (19.08%)	17 (5.23%)	2.52 (1.81 – 4.01)	2.04 (1.45 – 2.71)	0.003
Reduced personal accomplishment (n=325)						
	Low	Moderate	High			
Neuroticism	16 (4.92%)	16 (4.92%)	12 (3.69%)	0.85 (0.72 – 0.94)	1.08 (0.69 – 1.23)	0.004
Openness to experience	13 (4.00%)	19 (5.85%)	11 (3.38%)	3.91 (2.18 – 6.98)	2.41 (0.91 – 5.84)	0.022
Extraversion	19 (5.85%)	38 (11.67%)	8 (2.46%)	0.88 (0.58 – 1.11)	0.92 (0.69 – 1.08)	0.002
Agreeableness	58 (17.85%)	21 (6.46%)	18 (5.54%)	2.13 (1.94 – 5.01)	2.71 (2.59 – 4.41)	0.005
Conscientiousness	51 (15.69%)	15 (4.62%)	10 (3.08%)	0.69 (0.71 – 0.95)	2.21 (0.82 – 5.73)	0.003

COR: crude odds ratio, AOR= adjusted odds ratio, CI= confidence interval, Frequency (percentage)

Objective 1: Association between personality trait and burnout

The Table 2 presents the results of a logistic regression analysis examining the association between personality traits and burnout in midwives. The analysis revealed that neuroticism was significantly associated with emotional exhaustion (p=0.002), depersonalization (p=0.005), and reduced personal accomplishment (p=0.004). Midwives who exhibited high level of neuroticism were more likely to experience emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal

accomplishment. This is not surprising, as neuroticism is characterized by anxiety, anger, and vulnerability, which can increase the risk of burnout. The result also revealed that openness to experience was significantly associated with reduced personal accomplishment (p=0.022). Midwives who were open to experience were more likely to experience personal accomplishment. Openness to experience is often associated with creativity, flexibility, and resilience which helps to increase personal accomplishment of individuals.

Furthermore, the result in Table.2 showed that extraversion was significantly related with depersonalization (p=0.002) and reduced personal accomplishment (p=0.002). Midwives

who had moderate and high levels of extraversion were more likely to experience depersonalization and reduced personal accomplishment. This may be because extraverted midwives may be more likely to take on more responsibilities and engage in more social interactions, which could increase their stress levels and lead to burnout. Also, agreeableness was significantly associated with emotional exhaustion ($p=0.003$) and reduced personal accomplishment ($p=0.005$) as presented in Table.2 This implies that midwives who have high level of agreeableness were more likely to experience emotional exhaustion and reduced personal accomplishment. This may be because agreeable midwives may be more likely

to prioritize the needs of others over their own needs, which can lead to emotional exhaustion and reduced personal accomplishment. The Table .1 also showed that conscientiousness was significantly associated with emotional exhaustion ($p=0.001$), depersonalization ($p=0.003$), and reduced personal accomplishment ($p=0.003$). Midwives who scored high on conscientiousness were more likely to experience emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. This could be attributed to the fact that conscientious midwives may be more likely to take on more responsibilities and strive for perfection, which can increase their stress levels and lead to burnout.

Table 3: Association between emotional intelligence and burnout

Emotional intelligence	Level of emotional exhaustion (n=325)			COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)	P-value
	Low	Moderate	High			
Self-awareness	14 (4.31%)	58 (17.55%)	2 (0.62%)	1.21 (0.82 – 1.71)	0.76 (0.57 – 1.01)	0.001
Self-management	20 (6.15%)	8 (2.46%)	31 (9.54%)	0.41 (0.33 – 0.58)	0.53 (0.31 – 0.81)	0.005
Self-motivation	11 (3.38%)	52 (16.00%)	5 (1.54%)	0.79 (0.68 – 1.15)	0.81 (0.55 – 1.21)	0.04
Social awareness	10 (3.08%)	40 (12.31%)	9 (2.77%)	0.52 (0.43 – 0.86)	0.26 (0.08 – 0.85)	0.501
Relationship management	13 (4.00%)	41 (12.62%)	11 (3.38%)	1.10 (0.74 – 1.48)	1.23 (0.24 – 1.12)	0.003
Depersonalization (n=325)						
	Low	Moderate	High			
Self-awareness	11 (3.38%)	43 (13.23%)	8 (2.46%)	1.11 (0.79 – 1.51)	1.05 (0.83 – 1.31)	0.003
Self-management	21 (6.46%)	10 (3.08%)	29 (8.92%)	0.71 (0.50 – 0.94)	0.52 (0.39 – 0.70)	0.001

Self-motivation	13 (4.00%)	50 (15.38%)	8 (2.46%)	0.77 (0.53 – 0.92)	0.62 (0.46 – 0.85)	0.005
Social awareness	8 (2.46%)	48 (14.77%)	11 (3.38%)	0.91 (0.68 – 1.25)	0.58 (0.40 – 0.83)	0.080
Relationship management	14 (4.31%)	46 (14.15%)	5 (1.54)	1.20 (0.85 – 1.81)	1.52 (1.08 – 2.18)	0.002
Reduced personal accomplishment (n=325)						
	Low	Moderate	High			
Self-awareness	10 (3.08%)	32 (9.85%)	17 (5.26%)	1.72 (1.35 – 2.16)	0.91 (0.67 – 1.40)	0.001
Self-management	21 (6.46%)	41 (12.62%)	11 (3.38%)	1.50 (1.21 – 2.18)	0.86 (0.56 – 1.17)	0.001
Self-motivation	27 (8.31%)	40 (12.31%)	13 (4.00%)	0.81 (0.54 – 1.35)	0.52 (0.40 – 0.68)	0.005
Social awareness	21 (6.46%)	15 (4.62%)	9 (2.77%)	0.54 (0.37 – 0.76)	1.45 (0.98 – 1.70)	0.070
Relationship management	30 (9.23%)	18 (5.54%)	20 (6.15%)	0.48 (0.27 – 0.81)	1.32 (0.81 – 2.32)	0.002

COR: crude odds ratio, AOR= adjusted odds ratio, CI= confidence interval

Objective 2: Association between emotional intelligence and burnout

The logistic regression analysis examining the association between emotional intelligence and burnout among midwives is presented in Table 3. The result revealed that self-awareness was significantly related with emotional exhaustion (p=0.001), depersonalization (p=0.003), and reduced personal accomplishment (p=0.001). Midwives who recorded low level of self-awareness were more likely to experience burnout. This is not surprising, as self-awareness is the ability to recognize and understand one's own emotions and needs, which is essential for

managing stress and preventing burnout. The Table also showed that self-management was significantly associated with emotional exhaustion (p=0.005), depersonalization (p=0.001), and reduced personal accomplishment (p=0.001). Among the midwives, those who had low level of self-management were more likely to experience burnout. This is because self-management is the ability to regulate one's own emotions and behaviors, which is essential for managing stress and preventing burnout.

The Table.3 also showed that self-motivation was significantly associated with depersonalization (p=0.005) and reduced personal accomplishment (p=0.005). Midwives with

moderate or high of self-motivation were more likely not to experience burnout. This is because self-motivation is the ability to drive oneself to achieve goals and overcome obstacles, which is essential for managing stress and preventing burnout. Furthermore, relationship management was significantly related with emotional exhaustion ($p=0.003$), depersonalization ($p=0.002$), and reduced personal accomplishment ($p=0.002$). It was observed that midwives exhibited low level trait on relationship management were more likely to experience burnout. This is because relationship management is the ability to build and maintain strong relationships with others, which is essential for preventing burnout and improving job satisfaction.

Discussion of Findings

The majority of the midwives exhibited moderate trait on neuroticism, which could mean that most midwives tend to experience average levels of anxiety, anger, and vulnerability. However, a proportion of midwives, 14.16%, scored high on neuroticism, which can increase their risk of burnout this is because Widiger and Oltmanns (2017) observed that nurses with high trait on neuroticism may be more prone to stress, anxiety, and depression, which can negatively impact their physical and mental health, as well as their ability to provide high-quality patient care.

From the result, most midwives tend to be moderately open to new experiences, ideas, and perspectives. However, a proportion of the midwives, 15.00%, exhibited low openness to experience, and this can limit their ability to

adapt to changing situations and increase their risk of burnout. This is because openness to experience is characterized by a tendency to be curious, open-minded, and receptive to new ideas and experiences (Abu Raya et al., 2023). Midwives who have low openness to experience may be less likely to seek out new challenges and opportunities, which can lead to stagnation and burnout (Terry and Spendlove, 2025). With reference to extraversion, most midwives tend to be moderately outgoing and sociable. However, some midwives with low trait of extraversion can increase their risk of burnout if they are not able to manage their workload and stress levels effectively. McCabe and Fleeson (2012) explained that it's because extraversion is characterized by a tendency to be outgoing, sociable, and assertive. Midwives who score low on extraversion may be more introverted and less likely to seek out social support and interaction, which can lead to feelings of isolation and burnout.

Most midwives tend to be moderately agreeable. However, some of the midwives had low trait on agreeableness, which can increase their risk of burnout if they are not able to manage conflicts and difficult situations effectively. Reizer et al. (2023) opined that agreeableness is characterized by a tendency to be cooperative, compassionate, and sensitive to the needs of others. Midwives with low trait of agreeableness may be less likely to seek out support and collaboration from colleagues, which can lead to conflicts and burnout. Also, most midwives tend to be moderately conscientious. Those with low conscientiousness increase their risk of burnout

if they are not able to prioritize their tasks and manage their time effectively. Huo and Jiang (2021) observed that conscientiousness is the tendency to be organized, responsible, and dependable.

Midwives who experienced burnout tend to have low self-awareness, this shows that they may struggle with recognizing and understanding their own emotions and needs. Doherty and O'Brien, (2022) observed that lack of self-awareness can intensify burnout, as midwives may be less able to recognize the signs of burnout and take steps to manage their stress. The fact that 15.60% of the midwives recorded low on self-management indicates that some midwives may struggle with managing their own emotions and behaviors, which can aggravate burnout (Oates et al., 2019). The low level of self-motivation among midwives indicates that some midwives may struggle with finding meaning and purpose in their work, which can increase burnout. The midwives who experienced burnout were observed to have varying levels of social awareness. Jin et al. (2022) explained that some midwives may be more able to understand and empathize with the needs and emotions of others, while others may struggle with this. The high level of emotional exhaustion experienced by 24.56% of the respondents can be attributed to the demanding nature of midwifery work, which requires midwives to be emotionally invested in their patients' care and well-being (Buchanan et al., 2025). Hajiesmaello et al. (2022), reported that midwives are often exposed to high-stress situations, such as emergency deliveries and complications, which

can lead to feelings of depletion, fatigue, and cynicism

. A significant proportion of midwives were able to manage their emotional exhaustion effectively. This may be due to their ability to cope with stress, their support systems, or their work environments (Soósné Kiss et al., 2024). Ismaila et al. (2021) reported that midwives who have a strong support system, such as colleagues, family, and friends, may be better able to manage their emotional exhaustion. Interestingly, the levels of depersonalization experienced by the midwives can be attributed to the environment stress observed by the midwives, which can lead to emotional numbing and detachment (Altiparmak and Yilmaz, 2021). This finding is similar to the study of Brückner et al. (2024) who explained that, midwives who experience high levels of depersonalization may view their patients as objects rather than people, which can lead to a lack of emotional connection and a decrease in the quality of care provided. The low level of depersonalization observed by the midwives showed they were able to maintain a high level of emotional connection with their patients (Akova et al., 2021). This may be due to their ability to empathize with their patients, their positive attitudes towards their work, or their commitment to providing high-quality patient care.

The high level of reduced personal accomplishment experienced by the midwives can be attributed to the high expectations and demands placed on midwives, which can lead to feelings of inadequacy and self-doubt (Sangy et al., 2023). Furthermore, midwives who

experience high levels of reduced personal accomplishment may feel that they are not meeting the expectations of their patients, colleagues, or employers, which can lead to a decrease in their confidence and self-efficacy. This can be due to the fact that midwives are often held to high standards of care, and any mistakes or perceived shortcomings can lead to feelings of guilt and inadequacy (Leeming et al., 2022). On the other hand, the fact that some of the midwives recorded a low level of reduced personal accomplishment suggests that a proportion of midwives were able to maintain a high level of confidence and self-efficacy (Tzamakos et al., 2024). This may be due to their positive attitudes towards their work, their commitment to providing high-quality patient care, or their ability to reflect on their practice and identify areas for improvement (Flaubert et al., 2021)..

Conclusions

The study findings of this study revealed in-depth insights into midwives' personality and emotional intelligence and their relationship with burnout in selected public health facilities in Abia State.

Personality traits play a critical role in burnout susceptibility, with neuroticism being strongly associated with emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and reduced personal accomplishment. Highly conscientious, agreeable, and extraverted midwives also experience increased burnout risks due to their inclination to take on excessive responsibilities, maintain social engagement, and prioritize others' needs over their own. Conversely,

midwives with high openness to experience tend to find fulfillment in their work, reducing their vulnerability to burnout. Emotional intelligence significantly influences burnout levels, with low self-awareness, self-management, self-motivation, and relationship management being predictive of workplace stress. Midwives who struggle with regulating emotions, maintaining interpersonal connections, and finding intrinsic motivation are more likely to experience burnout, emphasizing the need for enhanced emotional intelligence training and coping mechanisms

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